

FACTORS INFLUENCING QUALITY OF WORK LIFE: AN ANALYSIS ON REGISTERED CONSTRUCTION WORKERS IN TIRUNELVELI DISTRICT OF INDIA

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Abstract

This research study aims to explore the factors influences of Quality of Work Life (QWL) among the registered construction workers. Quality of Work Life (QWL) refers to the favorableness or unfavorableness of a job environment for workers of an organization. Thus, quality of work life helps for development of human resources. QWL includes and motivates the employees to learn further for present and future roles. This study made an attempt to analysis of factors affecting QWL of registered construction workers in India. Five factors have identified (General well-being, working environment, job satisfaction, social security and grievance redress) through literature review. The result of the study is that three out of five factors have significant influence on QWL. It is statistically evidenced through regression analysis. Finally, this study concludes that insurance facilities, medical facilities, and grievance redressal leads to not satisfy by construction workers.

Keywords: Quality of Work Life, Construction Workers, Social Security, Grievance Redress

INTRODUCTION

In construction sectors is a second largest sector in unorganized industry after agricultural sector. This industry face number challenges including high level of health problems and accidents, construction being one of the most hazardous sectors (Weeks 2011). Hence, the QWL is a significant concept which needs some favorableness or unfavorableness of job environment for workers. This research is about identifying factors affecting QWL of construction workers. Dana and Griffin (1999) defined QWL is a holistic concept which considers both work based factors such as wage pay, interpersonal relationships and factors influencing life satisfaction and general well-being as influencers. However, the QWL is a favorableness or unfavorableness from employers in working environment. In this study, the researcher has identified few major factors that may affect the QWL factors such as General Well Being, Working Environment, Job Satisfaction, Social Security and Grievance Redressal. Besides, there are many factors are affecting the QWL of the workers. But, the researcher has identified

these factors are create impact more on construction workers as per current aspects of Indian context. Moreover, the meaning of QWL may vary to different people for different employees of the organizations. So, the primary objective of this research is to test the reliability of identified factors that influenced the QWL from registered construction workers in India.

OBJECTIVES

1. Determining the variables that affect the quality of work life of registered construction workers
2. Determining which variable plays the most significant role on quality of work life.
3. Establishing hypothesis on the basis of the research work.
4. Drawing a qualitative and quantitative conclusion on the basis of the survey.

LITERATURE REVIEW

There are numerical articles have been written on quality of work life in various sectors. But, a very few studies on unorganised sectors like agriculture labour, construction labour, beedi workers etc. In case of India the research articles in QWL on construction workers is very few. In this study the researcher has bring out few factors which is influencing more on construction workers. However, work is not a simple instrument or a mean of subsistence anymore; it is now a multifactor process, in which the human being is placed as a driving centre. Following the work evolution came the QWL, which have the focus centered on the individual, and its concerning, is to try to offer good laborer conditions to the worker, so that he can develop his tasks with satisfaction and well-being. According to **(Walton, 2005)** the better QWL is important for any industrial organizations to continue to absorb and hold workers. QWL is an inclusive programme designed to increase job performance of workers, improving learning process in workplace and facilitates workers to have better development and transition. Hence, studying the QWL concept is important to all the sectors. QWL refers to the favorableness or unfavorableness of a job environment for people **(Davis and Newstrom, 1985)**. Moreover, QWL is a big concept. QWL has been defined in various ways. According to **Rose (2006)** quality of work life is a philosophy or set of principles, which holds that people are trustworthy, responsible and capable of making a valuable contribution to the organization. It also involves respect and the elements that are relevant to an individual QWL include task, working environment, organizational culture, administrative system and the relationship between on the job and off the job life. **Taylor (1979)** described quality of working life as a holistic approach that includes: basic extrinsic job factors of wages, hours and working conditions, the intrinsic job notions of the nature of the work itself, authority exercised by employees, employee participation in decision making, fair and equal approach at work, social support, utilizing one's present skills, self-growth, a relevant scope of future at work, social relevance of the work or product, and effect on extra work activities. **Lau (2001)** measures QWL as the favorable working atmosphere that chains and promotes satisfaction by giving employees with rewards, job security and career development opportunity. Therefore QWL and its relationship

with employee health and performance has become an explicit objective for many of the human resource policies in modern organizations. According to **Mohammad BaitulIslam (2012)** the QWL refers a proper balance both in work and personal life which also ensure organizational productivity and employee's job satisfaction. The employees who feel that their organization is acting in a socially responsible manner, in terms of its products and services, will tend to value their work and careers more highly, which in turn is likely to enhance the self-esteem and well-being leading to a higher QWL (**Walton, 1975; Orpen, 1981**). According to **Michie and Williams (2003)**, poor supervisor support, long hours of work, and work overload factors are associated with psychological ill health. On the other hand, a good supervisor can also help one to use one's resources better and manage one's workload (**Hawkins and Shohet, 2000**). Social support colleagues refer to instrumental and emotional support provided by colleagues (**Van Der Doef and Maes, 1999**). To conclude, most of the studies have been focused job satisfaction and working environment situation. In the context of construction workers the most important factors that directly affect the quality of work life are general well-being, working conditions, job satisfaction, social security and grievance redressal. These factors are considered by the researcher to analysis the impact of QWL of the registered construction workers in India.

Conceptual Framework

A conceptual framework has been developed (Figure 1) that is one of the relative construct of this study.

Hypotheses Development

H1= General well-being has an impact on quality of work life of construction workers.

H2= Working environment affects quality of work life of registered construction workers.

H3= Job satisfaction affects quality of work life of the respondents.

H4= Social security has create an impact on quality of work life of the workers.

H5= Grievance redress affects quality of work life of the construction workers.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

Research Methodology is a way to systematically solve the research problem. The research methods constitute an important component of research methodology. It refers to all those methods adopted by the researcher in the course of analyzing and studying the research problem and to drive the logical solutions. A total of 592 sample size considered to be adequate for my study. Each and every response is checked thoroughly for incomplete and missing response. The interview schedule has two parts in were the first part contains some demographic information. In the second part, the questionnaire contains 120 items to construct the five independent variables along with dependent variable. The level of agreement scale has used to collect the data in this study such as 1-Strongly agree, 2-Agree, 3-Neutral, 4-Disagree, 5-Strongly disagree. An interview schedule were used as data collection tool for primary data

in both English and Tamil languages. Reliability analysis was done to identify the consistency of the data for analysis.

DATA ANALYSIS AND FINDINGS

1. Demographic profile

The table 1 shows that clearly demographic profile of the registered construction workers in Tirunelveli district of India. This study contains 82.44 percent male respondents and 17.56 percent female respondent. The researcher has been selected only ten categories of construction workers. Among them the largest 29.89 percent respondents lay hold mason and 22.12 percent of the respondents worked under helpers (cithal). Concrete workers is third largest 10.47 percent among them category of occupation followed by fitter (7.43), title workers (6.41), painter (6.08), carpenter (5.06), welder (4.89), electrician (4.28), plumber (3.37) percent respectively. Out of the total respondents the majority of them got married life with 81.78 percent followed by unmarried, widow, separated with 13.17 percent, 3.37 percent, and 1.68 percent respectively. Among them 39.52 percent respondent's age is in between 41-50 years and a 22.97 percent respondent is under above 51 years of age. Moreover, 17.90 percent and 17.59 percent is under 31-40, 21-30 ages of years respectively. Out of the total respondents 2.02 percent of them are below the age group of 20 years in the study area.

2. Reliability analysis

A reliability analysis is commonly used to identify the internal consistency of the variables, However, Cronbach's alpha is commonly used to test the reliability and the range of alpha coefficient value is in between 0 to 1. The higher value indicates the higher reliability (Hair, et al., 1992). A value more than .70 is significantly good measure for sufficient scale of reliability (1951, Nunnally, 1987). According to the cronbach's alpha test the value of alpha in my study is 0.842 (Table 2) which is higher than minimum acceptable value. Therefore, 84.20% of data are reliable in my study. This reliable analysis has been done for all dependent and independent variables. Besides, mean scores of the factors of QWL with standard deviation also shown (Table 4) in my study.

3. Hypotheses Testing

To conduct the hypothesis test a regression analysis has been done and six factors which have an effect in quality of work life are considered. However, details of the influence of independent variable over dependent variable have been shown in Table 7. First hypothesis was H1, General well-being has an impact on quality of work life of the construction workers. According to the analysis, the significance value for the hypothesis is 0.000, which is less than level of significance $\alpha = 0.05$. So, null hypothesis is rejected and H1 is accepted. Second hypothesis was H2, Working environment affects quality of work life of registered construction workers. According to the analysis, the significance value for the hypothesis is 0.034, which is less than level of significance $\alpha = 0.05$. So, null hypothesis is rejected and H2 is accepted. Third hypothesis was H3, Job satisfaction affects quality of work life of the respondents. In this case, the significance value for the hypothesis is 0.000, which is less than level of significance $\alpha =$

0.05. So, null hypothesis is rejected and H3 is accepted. The fourth hypothesis was H4, Social security has create an impact on quality of work life of the workers. Here, the significance value for the hypothesis is 0.437 which is more than level of significance $\alpha = 0.05$. So, the null hypothesis is accepted and H4 is rejected. My final hypothesis is grievance redress affects quality of work life of the construction workers. The significance value for the hypothesis is 0.583 which shows that more than level of significance $\alpha = 0.05$. Hence, research null hypothesis is accepted and H5 is rejected.

4. Regression analysis

From the regression analysis Table 5 the researcher found that R square value to be 0.352 meaning 35.2 percent of the variability in the QWL of employees in the registered construction workers in Tirunelveli District in India can be explained by these five independent factors. In this case the independent variables are general well-being, working environment, job satisfaction, social security and grievance redress. Moreover, QWL is dependent variables in this study. From the ANOVA table we see that the significance value is 0.000 (Table 6), thus proving that the model is valid and significant. However, among six factors three of them (general well-being, working environment, and job satisfaction) have positive and significance influence on QWL. The other two factors named social security and grievance redressal have no significance impact on QWL. Probably, respondents have given less notice on it.

LIMITATION

This study confined few limitations. Though the researcher has framed interview schedule to meet out the respondents to collect the data is so difficult due to illiterate and non-availability of work. In some cases, the topics were not understood by the workers and hesitated to disclose their information. Moreover, the respondents are selected only form Tirunelveli District: therefore this research does not reflect the socio economic and living conditions. However unwillingness of respondents was another big limitation in this research. The R Square (0.352) is comparatively low which means that other factors can also influence the quality of work life of the registered construction workers in Tirunelveli District of India.

CONCLUSION and RECOMMENDATION

This study is tried to examine the factors that have an impact on QWL of registered construction workers in Tirunelveli district. In this study the researcher has indentified five factors namely, general well-being, working environment, job satisfaction, social security and grievance redress. The result of the regression analysis shows that out of five factors three factors are strongly significant influence on QWL. The remaining two factors (social security and grievance redress) have not influence on QWL of the respondents. Hence, Labour and welfare board may come forward to assessment of the social security of the construction workers. This social security measures may be improved through insurance facilities, medical facilities, old age protection schemes and other infrastructural facilities. Moreover, the proper grievance redressal procedure is also being conducted properly as per the board of construction and welfare department to improve their QWL.

Figure 1: Conceptual frame work of factors influencing Quality of Work Life:

Table 1 -Demographic Profile of Respondent

S.No	Demographic Profile	Frequency	Percentage	
1.	Gender	Male	488	82.44
		Female	104	17.56
		Total	592	100.00
2.	Category of Occupation	Mason	177	29.89
		Carpenter	30	5.06
		Title workers	38	6.41
		Concrete workers	62	10.47
		Fitter	44	7.43
		Electrician	25	4.28
		Welder	29	4.89
		Painter	36	6.08
		Plumber	20	3.37
		Cithal	131	22.12
		Total	592	100.00
3.	Marital Status	Married	484	81.78
		Unmarried	78	13.17
		Separated	10	1.68
		Widow	20	3.37
		Total	592	100.00
4.	Age	Below 20	12	2.02
		21-30	104	17.59
		31-40	106	17.90
		41-50	235	39.52
		Above 51	136	22.97
		Total	592	100.00

Source: Field survey

Table 2 - Reliability Statistics

Cronbach's Alpha	Cronbach's Alpha Based on Standardized Items	No. of Items
0.842	0.841	592

Source: Field survey

Table 3 - Reliability Tests

Factors Name	Items	Value
Quality of Work Life (Dependent)	20	0.829
General Well Being	20	0.819
Working Environment	20	0.835
Job Satisfaction	20	0.798
Social Security	20	0.802
Grievance Redress	20	0.810

Source: Field survey

Table 4 – Mean and Standard Division of QWL

Factors	Mean	SD
General Well Being	2.894	0.512
Working Environment	2.996	0.527
Job Satisfaction	3.208	0.508
Social Security	3.196	0.657
Grievance Redress	3.879	0.612

Source: Field survey

Table 5 - Results of Regression Analysis – Quality of Work Life

Model Summary

R	R Square	Adjusted Square	R	Std. Error of the Estimate
0.593	0.352	0.346		0.414

a. Predictors: (Constant), GR, WE, GWB, JS and SS.\

Table 6 -ANOVA

	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Regression	54.583	5	10.917	63.637	0.000
Residual	100.525	586	0.172		
Total	155.109	591			

a. Predictors: (Constant): GR, WE, GWB, JS and SS.

b. Dependent Variable: QWL

Table 7: Coefficients

	Unstandardized Coefficients B	Std. Error	Standardized Coefficients Beta	t	Sig.
(Constant)	0.909	0.139		6.546	0.000
GWB	0.279	0.040	0.287	6.968	0.000
WE	0.086	0.041	0.086	2.124	0.034
JS	0.260	0.036	0.333	7.176	0.000
SS	0.032	0.042	0.039	0.777	0.437
GR	-0.024	0.044	-0.026	-0.549	0.583

a. Dependent Variable: QWL

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